

Studies in Formation and Properties of Carbon-Sulphur Surface Complexes. Part VII. Effect of the Complexes on Surface Behaviour of Carbon Blacks

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Manuscript received 5 May 1973; accepted 7 June 1973

Irreversible fixation of sulphur on Mogul-A and Spheron-4 by treatment with sulphur, hydrogen sulphide and carbon disulphide at 600° alters the shape and contents of the water vapour isotherms (35°) indicating a development of porosity and trends for capillary condensation. Additional fixation of sulphur tends to reduce moisture sorption at all r.v.p.'s indicating partial filling of capillary pores and a fall in the available surface area due to a partial coverage of particles with sulphur. The specific surface areas of both the carbon black samples, before and after various fixations of sulphur, were determined from CO₂-isotherms at 0° and pressures upto 200 torr by applying Polanyi potential theory as modified by Dubinin. The values obtained are in harmony with the above views. The catalytic activity of each carbon black increases sharply on fixation of a small amount of sulphur showing that the associated sulphur is combined chemically. The activity, however, starts falling on continued fixation of sulphur, although the value remains invariably higher than that of the original sample.

THE formation of carbon-sulphur surface complexes on treatment of carbon blacks with sulphur, carbon disulphide and hydrogen sulphide at 600° was reported in the previous publication¹. The present work was undertaken to examine the effect of the combined sulphur on certain surface characteristics of the resulting products which may give some insight into the mechanism of fixation of sulphur.

Experimental

Two samples of carbon black (Spheron-4 and Mogul-A), outgassed at 1000° to free them essentially of combined oxygen, were treated with sulphur, carbon disulphide and hydrogen sulphide^{2,3} at 600° for different intervals of time so as to get fixation of different amounts of sulphur. The products were extracted exhaustively with carbon disulphide to remove physically held sulphur, if any, and then dried in an air oven (120°) and stored over nitrogen till required for use. The amount of sulphur fixed in each case was estimated by Eschka's method⁴.

Water vapour adsorption isotherms were determined gravimetrically at 35° using McBain's balance technique. Carbon dioxide adsorption isotherms were obtained at 0° by using the well known B.E.T. technique generally employed in the study of low-temperature gaseous adsorption. The catalytic decomposition of aqueous hydrogen peroxide was studied by adding 0.25 g. material to 25 ml of 1.5 *M* H₂O₂, keeping the suspension in an incubator maintained at 35° (±0.1°) for 24 hr and determining the fall in the concentration by titrating an aliquot against standard KMnO₄ in the usual way.

Results and Discussion

The water vapour adsorption isotherms on 1000°-outgassed samples of Spheron-4 and Mogul-A, before and after fixation of varying amounts of sulphur, on treatment with sulphur vapour at 600°, are plotted in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively. It is seen that the isotherms before fixation of sulphur are of type III of the well known classification and do not indicate any significant capillary condensation except, perhaps, at vapour pressures close to the saturation vapour pressure. After fixation of sulphur, however, the isotherms change into type IV, indicating capillary condensation trends and development of porosity in each carbon black. It is interesting to note that fixation of sulphur even to the extent of 0.52 mg. atom/g. (i.e., ~1.6% by weight), as in the case of Spheron-4, raises moisture sorption significantly at all relative vapour pressures (r.v.p.) < 0.75 and a fall thereafter. Further fixation of sulphur, in each sample, tends to reduce moisture sorption at all r.v.p.'s, although the isotherms retain the shape characteristic of type IV. The fall in moisture sorption appears to be due to partial filling of capillary pores, making them less and less accessible to water molecules, and decrease in effective surface area due to coverage of particles with sulphur. The fact that the maximum sorption value at ~0.95 r.v.p. continues to fall with increase in the amount of sulphur fixed shows that an appreciable fraction of the surface is being covered by sulphur.

The isotherms on Spheron-4, after fixation of various amounts of sulphur on treatment with carbon disulphide, also show the same trends. The remarkable increase in the sorption values at r.v.p.'s < 0.75,

on fixation of only 0.2 mg. atom of sulphur, is quite significant and so is subsequent fall on additional fixation of sulphur.

in Figs. 4 and 5. The values of V_m , were obtained from the respective intercepts at $\log_{10} (P_0/P) = 0$. The specific surface area values of the various

Fig. 1. Water vapour adsorption isotherms (35°) on 1000°-outgassed Spheron-4 before and after fixation of sulphur on treatment with carbon disulphide vapour. O—O. Before fixation, ●—● 0.52 mg atom sulphur/g, □—□ 0.88 mg atom sulphur/g, X—X 1.2 mg atom/g; Δ—Δ 1.49 mg atom sulphur/g.

In order to get some further insight, it was thought of interest to determine specific surface areas of the carbon blacks before and after fixation of varying amounts of sulphur. The B.E.T. method, based on low-temperature adsorption of nitrogen, has been criticised in recent years by several workers^{5,6} on the ground that the range of applicability of this method extends into the pressure range where capillary condensation of nitrogen is likely to occur. The value of V_m obtained by this technique, therefore, gives a measure of micropore volume instead of micropore area. Lamond and Marsh⁵ as well as Walker and Shelef⁷, and Mahajan, Morishita and Walker⁸ have therefore, applied Polanyi potential theory⁹, as modified by Dubinin¹⁰, to the calculation of surface area from adsorption of carbon dioxide at 0° and at pressures < 220 torr which is far below the saturation pressure (34.46 atm.) of carbon dioxide at this temperature. The thickness of carbon dioxide molecule (3.3 Å)¹¹, being close to that of nitrogen molecule (3.68 Å),¹² but the conditions being such that no capillary condensation is possible, Dubinin equation permits the calculation of a more realistic value of V_m as monolayer capacity as distinct from volume capacity.

The Dubinin plots of $\log^2 (P_0/P)$ against $\log V$, where V is the volume of carbon dioxide adsorbed at pressure P in the case of Mogul-A and Spheron-4, before and after fixation of various amounts of sulphur, on treatment with sulphur vapour, are shown

samples, taking the molecular area of carbon dioxide⁷ as 17 Å², are recorded in Table 1. Similar graphs for H₂S-treated and CS₂-treated products were also obtained but are not given for reasons of space. It is seen, in the first instance, that the surface area, after fixation of a small amount of sulphur in the initial stages, by treatment with sulphur or hydrogen sulphide, undergoes hardly any significant change. The water isotherms of these samples, as already discussed, however, indicate considerable formation of micropores involved in the sorption of water vapour at lower relative vapour pressures. The surface area, obtained from Dubinin's plots, which includes micropore area, therefore, should have been higher. It appears that any increase in surface area due to this fact is more or less compensated for by partial coverage of the surface by deposition of sulphur on carbon particles.

The value of surface area, however, falls substantially thereafter on continued fixation of additional amounts of sulphur. This appears to be due not only to filling in of some of the micropores, which may consequently become less and less accessible to the CO₂ molecule, but also due to a fall in the geometric area on account of additional coverage of the particles by sulphur.

The specific surface area values on treatment with carbon disulphide follow slightly different trends. The values increase considerably after fixation of a

small amount of sulphur in the initial stages for Mogul-A as well as Spheron-4. This appears to be due to the simultaneous deposition of carbon granules in an extremely fine state of sub-division in this reaction, as reported in a previous publications³. However, the values undergo a considerable fall with additional fixation of sulphur as observed in the case of products obtained from reactions with sulphur and hydrogen sulphide.

Magaril and Aksenova¹³ have shown that chemically combined sulphur increases the catalytic activity of carbon a black for decomposition of aqueous hydrogen peroxide. They treated their carbon black with a solution of sulphur in benzene and subsequently freed the physically held sulphur by heat treatment at 900°. It was thought of interest to check the catalytic activity of Mogul-A and Spheron-4 for this

reaction before and after fixation of different amounts of sulphur by the various treatments. The results of these experiments are included in Table 1. It is seen that the association of even a small amount of sulphur by any of the treatments considerably raises the catalytic activity of both the samples of carbon black. This does not substantiate the view of some previous workers¹⁴ that sulphur associated with carbon is held merely as a polymer in the micro-capillary pores.

It may be argued that the increased decomposition of hydrogen peroxide is due to the oxidation of the combined sulphur in carbon blacks. But this seems to be hardly the case, since there was no significant fall in the sulphur contents of the samples used, after reaction with hydrogen peroxide.

Fig. 2. Water vapour adsorption isotherms (35°) on 1000°-outgassed Mogul-A before and after fixation of sulphur on treatment with sulphur vapour. O—O Before fixation. ●—● 0.75mg atom sulphur/g, □—□ 1.36 mg atom sulphur/g, Δ—Δ 2.32 mg sulphur/g.

Fig. 3. Water vapour adsorption isotherms (35°) on 1000°-outgassed Spheron-4 before and after fixation of sulphur on treatment with sulphur vapour. O—O Before fixation, ●—● 0.20 mg atom sulphur/g, □—□ 0.52 mg atom sulphur/g, Δ—Δ 0.93 mg atom sulphur/g.

Fig. 4. Dubinin plots for CO₂ adsorption (0°) on 1000°-outgassed Mogul-A before and after fixation of sulphur on treatment with sulphur vapour. O—O. Before fixation, ●—● 0.75 mg atom sulphur/g, □—□ 1.36 mg atom sulphur/g, Δ—Δ 2.32 mg atom sulphur/g.

Fig. 5. Dubinin plots for CO_2 adsorption (0°) on 1000° -outgassed Spheron-4 before and after fixation of sulphur on treatment with sulphur vapour. O—O Before fixation, ●—● 0.52 mg atom sulphur/g, Δ — Δ 1.49 mg atom sulphur/g.

TABLE I. SPECIFIC SURFACE AREAS AND CATALYTIC ACTIVITIES OF MOGUL-A AND SPHERON-4 BEFORE AND AFTER FIXATION OF SULPHUR

Sulphurising reagent used	Amount of sulphur fixed (mg atom/g)	Specific surface area (m^2/g)	Amount of H_2O_2 decomposed (m. mole/g)
1	2	3	4
<i>Mogul-A, outgassed at 1000°</i>			
	Nil	207	50.6
Sulphur vapour	0.75	203	118.4
" "	1.36	159	102.3
" "	2.32	105	68.7
Hydrogen sulphide gas	0.27	—	59.4
" "	0.44	209	90.6
" "	0.82	153	72.4
Carbon disulphide vapour	0.70	249	97.2
" "	1.03	192	80.5
" "	1.65	159	74.4
<i>Spheron-4, outgassed at 1000°</i>			
	Nil	135	13.5
Sulphur vapour	0.52	117	26.3
" "	0.88	104	31.4
" "	1.49	95	26.7
Hydrogen sulphide gas	0.15	126	31.3
" "	0.55	113	—
" "	0.82	102	16.1
Carbon disulphide vapour	0.20	178	18.3
" "	0.52	104	27.5
" "	0.93	49	17.3

The catalytic activity of a carbon for the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide is known to increase with rise in its pH values¹⁷. But in the present case there was hardly any change in the pH values of the carbon black samples after fixation of sulphur. The remarkable increase in the catalytic activity after association of a small amount of sulphur, therefore, can only be attributed to a greater heterogeneity of the surface due to chemical fixation of sulphur as reported by Magaril and Aksenova (loc. cit.). It may be noted that similar fixation of nitrogen¹⁵ or iodine¹⁶ has also been reported to cause a raise in the catalytic activity of charcoal and carbon black for this reaction.

There is another aspect of the data which has not been reported by previous workers. The catalytic activity, after a sharp rise initially, starts declining on continued fixation of sulphur, although the value remains invariably higher than that of the original sample. This may be explained as partly due to a fall in the surface area, as reported in column 3 of the Table, and partly due to the inaccessibility of some of the sites located within the micropores which become increasingly blocked, as indicated by the water isotherms. The catalytic activity, however, can be related neither with the sulphur content nor with the specific surface area. This is because of various other factors, including microporosity, being involved as well.

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